

Developing Sensitive and Specific Diagnostic Screening Molecular Markers for Colon Cancer

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Colon cancer is a preventable malignancy if detected early enough before the cancer metastasizes. This cancer requires a lengthy period of time (≤ 20 years) for it to develop. As a result, screening for the early adenoma would need to be carried out less frequently than a test for an advanced form of cancer. On the other hand, as small number of adenomas would progress to full malignancy, the detection of these adenomas involves overtreatment of patients, and thus would incur costly screening, and thus will be harmful to patients. It should be emphasized that an optimum screening test for colon cancer would be one that allows only for the detection of those adenomas that are destined to advance to full malignancy.

Clinical management of colon cancer entails removing of adenomas at the time of their early detection by using colonoscopy screening of individuals. However, eligible participants may not wish to undertake this invasive and relatively expensive test because of the need for performing bowel preparation, the requirement for dietary restriction, preponderance of abdominal pain, potential perforation of the colon and --in some cases-- morbidity. Currently, the widely employed inexpensive fecal occult blood test (FOBT) lacks sensitivity. Due to the desirability of using a noninvasive reliable test acceptable to the target population as an initial screen, investigators have looked at developing molecular approaches. Important considerations that must be taken into account when developing such tests include: nature of the specimen (invasive *versus* non-invasive), type of specimen (stool, blood, or any other body fluid), stability of specimen when manipulated outside the body, number of collected specimens (one sample, or multiple samples taken over consecutive dates), and how the specimens are stored (room temperature *versus* frozen, and delivered posted or collected, *etc.*). Processing of samples needs to be accepted by the laboratory staff who will perform the tests. Any test that can be automated would be much more acceptable to technicians performing the assay, and will be cheaper to apply on a large scale.

In developing countries, colon cancer has been found to be on the rise because of adoption of a Western-type diet that is rich in fats and carbohydrates, and low in essential vitamins and minerals. Moreover, it is often not possible to perform colonoscopy because it is expensive, and

there are not enough trained gastroenterologists to carry out these specialized tests. We have shown that the quantitative changes in the expression of a few micro(mi)RNA genes in non-invasive stool [1], or minimally-invasive blood [2] that are associated with colon cancer have allowed for the development of more sensitive and specific molecular markers than those currently available for colon cancer. A miRNA approach in stool could particularly meet the criteria for test acceptability because it is noninvasive, requires less than 1 g of stool, results for stool were shown to be similar to those found in colon tissue, sampling on consecutive dates is not needed, samples can be mailed using cold packs, the method differentiates normal tissue from colon adenomas/carcinomas with high sensitivity and specificity, and the method is automatable, making it relatively inexpensive and more suited for early detection when compared to another more demanding molecular test such as mutated DNA markers.

An approach using nondegradable miRNAs molecules extracted from stool or blood by available commercial kits, would thus be preferable to a transcriptomic messenger (m)RNA-, mutation DNA-, epigenetic- or a proteomic-based test. Therefore, a non-invasive miRNA test in stool based on high throughput automated technologies and quantitative gene expression measurements commonly employed in diagnostic clinical laboratories will make a significant impact on colon cancer prevention by improving the noninvasive detection of this preventable disease at the early TNM disease stages (0-I).

The availability on the market of powerful high throughput approaches for global miRNA characterization, such as microarrays and simpler, universally applicable quantification assays for miRNA expression such as quantitative PCR assays, suggests that the validation pipeline that often encounters bottlenecks would be more efficient for a miRNA assay. Eventually, these validated tests can be placed on chips for a more convenient testing, as has been carried out in the detection of genetically modified organisms (GMOs) in food [3].

References

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